

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SPECIFIC EPISTEMIC COMPONENTS OF SCIENTIFIC DIALOGUE

Chalova O.

Doctoral Student of the Department of Theoretical and Applied Linguistics
of Minsk State Linguistic University

Abstract

The article discusses the epistemic parameters of scientific dialogue as a unique type of scientific discourse. It identifies and characterizes those epistemic components of scientific dialogue that can hardly be found in any other genre of scientific communication. It also describes the main functional aspects of speech acts reflecting the speaker's epistemic status.

Keywords: scientific discourse, scientific dialogue, epistemic components, mode of belief / disbelief, mode of ignorance, speech act, pragmatic features, pragmatic modifications.

Introduction. This work is of pragmalinguistic character and involves describing specific epistemic zones of *scientific dialogue* as a special type of scientific discourse which is structured as an exchange of scientists' opinions at a scientific forum of any format (scientific conferences, seminars, etc.). What is meant by *a discourse epistemic zone* is the mental state of affairs in the structure of the discourse (opinion, supposition, knowledge, etc.), a set of means and operators that express a speaker's subjective epistemic attitude to the propositional part of a speech act (thus showing if the speaker subjectively considers this part of the sentence to be true / factually correct or false / factually incorrect). At the same time, *a specific epistemic zone* is represented by those epistemic components that 1) occur only in scientific dialogue and cannot be found in any other genre of scientific discourse; 2) occur in other scientific genres but not so often as in scientific dialogue and are able to modify the pragmatics of discourse.

While *the traditional epistemic components of scientific discourse* include *knowledge* and *opinion*, *specific epistemic components of scientific dialogue* comprise *belief* and *ignorance* expressed in speech acts with the relevant explicit mode (either the mode of ignorance or belief), i. e. sentences containing the lexemes *believe* and *not to know* and their derivatives (*I believe that ... We don't know that ...*). Of course, the mode of belief in the English language is very close to the mode of opinion but isn't equal to it as 1) the verb *believe* is often defined through the verb *feel*: *to believe = to feel certain*, and 2) speech acts with the verb *believe* in a scientific dialogue often sound expressive (*We believe that trying to do that should be banned. No question*). The use of speech acts with the modes of ignorance and belief in scientific dialogue is predetermined by the dialogical format of communication (known for being spontaneous, expressive and emotive). On the one hand, speech acts of this type contradict the basic principles of scientific discourse (objectivity, clarity, etc.), but on the other hand their presence in scientific dialogue makes it a special genre of scientific discourse.

This very paper *aims at* describing the structural and pragmatic character of speech acts containing either the mode of ignorance or the mode of belief, which

is important through the necessity to study the epistemic and functional parameters of discourse as closely connected. The problem of epistemic components has been raised in just a few works none of which is on the basis of scientific discourse [1–5], which makes our paper timely. *The methods* of contextual and pragmalinguistic analysis have been used. *The research material* includes transcripts of modern scientific discussions (in English): a) Nanotechnology, Medicine, and Ethics; b) Digital Bioarchaeological Ethics Panel Discussion; c) Conscience in the Practice of the Health Professions; d) National Ethics Commissions: Looking Back and Looking Forward; e) Math/Science Partnerships Workshop. How People Learn.

Results and discussion.

Speech acts with specific epistemic modes in a scientific dialogue.

The corpus of our research material shows that speech acts with specific epistemic components (belief / disbelief and ignorance) have some peculiarities in scientific dialogue. The main of them are as follows.

1. Formal, semantic and pragmatic features of speech acts with specific epistemic modes in scientific dialogue.

As already been said, the phenomenon of *belief* is very similar to the category of opinion, but differs from it by a more subjective and volitional nature. Statements with the mode of belief in scientific dialogue are characterized by a greater degree of expressiveness (compared to statements with the mode of opinion), which is predetermined by the specific nature of the verb *believe* and pragmatic characteristics of scientific dialogue (*And I do believe that there is a fairness component here, or an equity component*). As for statements with *the mode of ignorance*, the degree of their expressiveness is also quite high: as is known, an expressive effect is created through something that deviates from the standard use, the way explicit appeals to ignorance do as they are not a standard form of scientific discourse (*We need to have forums or fora, whatever the plural might be, where we actually tell, and we need to be held accountable for our statements, somehow. I don't know how. The reality is that the word mechanism, you know, the word mechanism works against us. Let's be honest about this*).

Our observations demonstrate the statements with the mode of belief to be usually characterized by the

positive form of realization (*I believe that... They believe that...*), rather than negative (*I don't believe... They don't believe that...*): *Now, there is nothing wrong with that. And I do believe that there are meta-cognitive approaches and standards that are field-specific.* At the same time, speech acts with the mode of disbelief (*I don't believe / We don't believe*) are also a feature of scientific dialogue intensifying the emotional background of communication, enhancing the emotive properties of dialogue (*There used to be a time when people thought that there were magic markers that you could use to say, "This person's got cancer". We don't believe that any more*). What is special about statements with the mode of belief and disbelief in scientific dialogue is that they often have a complex pragmatic nature, for instance can function as a critical statement (*And sometimes people are probably fooling themselves about what they believe*).

As for speech acts with the mode of ignorance, their form of manifestation is always negative (*I don't know / We don't know*, e. g. *What we actually are doing is...instigating perhaps a very dangerous behavior...we don't know where it's going to go. So that's one thing. The final thing...is about morals*). In scientific dialogue, appeals to ignorance focus not only on demonstrating the absence of information, but also on performing other communicative tasks, in particular manifesting the speaker's directive intentions: **We don't know what the heck is going on, and so I'm concerned about that and I'm delighted that people are working on this and the more they work in on it, the better it is.** This context shows that the speaker implicitly makes people understand it to be high time to work on the problem the hardest possible way.

Thus, speech acts with the explicit modes of either belief / disbelief or ignorance play a very important pragmatic role in scientific dialogue: they do not only show the speaker's mental status, but also perform different pragmatic functions in scientific dialogue (like a critical statement) as well as intensify the expressive character of the type of communication under study.

2. The subject (agent) and object (target) of speech acts with specific epistemic modes in scientific dialogue.

In scientific dialogue, *the subject (the author of the statement)* of belief / disbelief and ignorance is either the speaker themselves (*We didn't know enough. And I believe Janet sent all of you a request for those things which you were looking for and hoping to walk away with*) or some other person (*And another is my knowledge of what I think students believe or know*). The first type of statement is represented by 1st-person constructions demonstrating the communicant's willingness to take an epistemic responsibility for evaluating the proposition, while the other type is about shifting the epistemic responsibility to other people.

As for *the object of belief/disbelief* (something what the belief is about), it is quite wide in scientific dialogue. The object of belief / disbelief can cover the following phenomena / actions / properties: **the experience of other countries** (*The number of embryos that are formed are often in excess of the two, I believe, that*

at least some countries limit implantation), **professional behavior of an expert in particular situations** (*I believe it is ethically permissible to sedate dying patients to the point of unconsciousness if the intended and direct effect of the sedation is to relieve distressing symptoms that are refractory to other treatments*), **a verbal or non-verbal act of a colleague** (*The way I disagree with Dr. Curlin is I believe Dr. Curlin has confused two very different concepts*), **the future state of affairs** (*So that is an area I believe would help if there are some sort of additional comment included in this report with regard to those potential confounding factor*), etc. As can be seen, in scientific dialogue, references to belief / disbelief can not only make a statement about the object of belief, not only perform certain pragmatic tasks (serve as a means of expressing critical assessment, as in the example above: see the sentence about Dr. Curling), but also serve as a method of regulating the course of the dialogue: *I believe we've reached the end of useful discussion* (here, the reference to belief is used as a signal to finish the discussion and can be interpreted as a means of regulating dialogical relations).

The object of ignorance is also variable. Our data show that the object of ignorance can cover **the way to perform an action/solve a problem** (*Whether we do that consciously to subconsciously, I don't know but we are getting what we are getting up to do from the day one, perhaps developing different ways of setting priorities and directing research infrastructure can be – can address some of this*), **the identity of people who can use the product you make** (*Because I think someone mentioned in one of the talks that once it's out there you don't know who's going to download it, who's going to print, and that's scary for bioarchaeologists*), **the nature of the interlocutor's intentions (in particular, communicative intentions)** (*So I don't know if you want to add to it, Alex, but that's a quick answer for you, Alfonso*) and other phenomena / processes / actions / qualities. As well as references to belief, references to ignorance are designed to implement different communicative tasks varying from pragmatic functions (for example, expressing doubt: see the context above about the necessity to permit access to a certain product and information) to dialogical functions (regulation of the course of the dialogue: see the context about Alex above).

Thus, speech acts of both belief / disbelief and ignorance are quite diverse in terms of their subject and object, which shows their ability to both cover different discussion topics and perform significant pragmatic functions and, consequently, their importance in scientific dialogue.

To fully understand the nature of speech acts with the explicit modes of ignorance and belief / disbelief functioning in scientific dialogue, it's necessary to focus on the following. While appeals to ignorance always have an explicitly expressed subject (i. e. they are *subject-oriented*), appeals to belief can be both subject-oriented and object-oriented. **Object-oriented speech acts** have an implicit subject (*it's hard to believe, I was heard and believed, they are believed*). However, such

impersonal and passive constructions are used less frequently in scientific dialogue in case the speaker is concentrated rather on the object of his / her epistemic assessment than on the subject. Most statements with the mode of belief are *subject-oriented*, which means that they have an explicit subject (*these people believe, experts believe, students believe, psychiatrists believe, etc.*) and appear in those contexts in which the speaker considers it important to emphasize the epistemic state of a particular person or group of persons.

Conclusions.

1. Despite a wide range of varieties of speech acts with the modes of belief / disbelief and ignorance, the use of them in scientific dialogue is limited by the principles and norms of scientific communication (informativeness, logic, clarity, objectivity, etc.).

2. Statements with an explicit mode of ignorance have a very weak discrediting potential (do not undermine the speaker's professional status) as they usually show a lack of knowledge in the sphere in which the speaker is not supposed to be an expert.

3. Speech acts with an explicit mode of belief / disbelief and ignorance are quite an appropriate component in scientific dialogue since they perform a number of important pragmatic functions.

4. Statements with an explicit mode of believe / disbelief and ignorance make scientific dialogue different from the other types of scientific discourse, determine its uniqueness in the structure of scientific communication.

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